

THE MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF METALLIC OXIDES AND THEIR MOLECULAR STRUCTURES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THOSE OF COBALT.

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Magnetic susceptibility values of different samples of cobaltous, cobaltous and cobaltic oxides, prepared in different ways, have been measured. The observed values of μ_s have been utilised to discuss the molecular constitution of the cobalt oxides.

The measurement of magnetic properties of compounds has been extensively employed to establish their constitution. No systematic attempt, however, has been made to investigate the magnetic properties of metallic oxides. Different workers report widely divergent results of the magnetic susceptibilities of the oxides of transition metals and there are few precise determinations of the variation of χ with temperature.

Thus in literature the values of the susceptibility of chromic oxide are given by Meyer (*Ann. Physik*, 1899, **68**, 325; **69**, 236) as 24.0×10^{-6} ; Moles and Gonzales (*Annal. Fis. Quim.*, 1923, **21**, 204) as 26.7×10^{-6} ; Wedekind and co-workers (*Ber.*, 1915, **48**, 105) as 25.97×10^{-6} and Huttig (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1933, **39**, 368) as varying between 28 to 47×10^{-6} . For the susceptibility of chromium dioxide, Moles and Gonzales (*loc. cit.*) gave a value of 42.2×10^{-6} , while Albercht and Wedekind (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, **210**, 105) reported a value of 36.0×10^{-6} . Further the value of χ obtained by Wedekind and Horst (*Ber.*, 1915, **48**, 105) for manganous oxide was 56.16×10^{-6} , for manganosic oxide 65.5×10^{-6} and for manganese dioxide 46.58×10^{-6} , whereas Theodorides (*Compt. rend.*, 1920, **171**, 948) found 67.46×10^{-6} as the χ value for manganosic oxide, Feytis (*Compt. rend.*, 1911, **152**, 710) 74.3×10^{-6} for manganosic oxide, Meyer (*loc. cit.*) and Wistrand ("Magnetiska susceptilitaten hos Kwart, etc." Upsala, 1916) 27.0×10^{-6} and 32.3×10^{-6} respectively for the dioxide. Similarly for vanadium pentoxide, Wedekind and Horst (*Ber.*, 1912, **45**, 262; 1915, **48**, 105) found the magnetic susceptibility value to be 0.16×10^{-6} while Meyer (*loc. cit.*) gave 0.95×10^{-6} and Berkman and Zocher (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, **124**, 318) 0.39×10^{-6} , and for uranosic oxide, Honda (*Ann. Physik*, 1910, **iv**, **32**, 1844) found χ as 4.34×10^{-6} ; while Wedekind and Horst (*loc. cit.*) reported 0.95×10^{-6} . Ferric oxide is usually paramagnetic but also exists in a ferro-magnetic form both in nature and as a synthetic product.

Similar observations have been made for cobalt and nickel oxides, for the latter it has been shown by Bhatnagar and Bal (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 603) that traces of metallic nickel present as an impurity account for the anomalous results.

The marked divergence in values of magnetic characteristics of oxide probably reflects their extreme variability in composition and the difficulty of obtaining them in a pure state. Recent work by Bhatnagar, King and collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1433) on the study of the magnetic susceptibilities of chromium and manganese oxides supports this view and they have shown that the differences are due to impurities, in particular, to small amounts of chemisorbed gases.

The present work deals with the oxides of cobalt which have elicited good deal of controversy. While Beetz (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1844, 61, 472) found cobaltous oxide to be non-magnetic, Williams (*Phys. Rev.*, 1926, ii, 26, 127) reported it as ferromagnetic, Hausknecht ("Magneto-chemische Untersuchungen," Strassburg, 1914, 18) gave 67×10^{-6} for its magnetic susceptibility and Herroun and Wilson (*Proc. Phys. Soc.*, 1921, 33, 204) 74.5×10^{-6} . In the case of cobaltous oxides Co_2O_4 , Merck and Wedekind (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 182, 49) found $\chi = 32 \times 10^{-6}$. Hausknecht (*loc. cit.*) 34.4×10^{-6} and Herroun and Wislon (*loc. cit.*) 39.6×10^{-6} to 43.6×10^{-6} , whereas Schwarzenberg, (*Annalen*, 1855, 97, 212) stated that it is non-magnetic. The magnetic properties of cobaltic oxide, Co_2O_3 , have not been studied.

It is clear from this resume that it would be useless to try to elucidate the molecular structure of the cobalt oxides with the help of these controversial χ -values.

It is well known that changes in principal valency bring about changes in magnetic moment which can be correlated with atomic structure. In general, atoms or ions which contain completed sub-groups possess zero or very small magnetic moment and are consequently diamagnetic, whilst those in which the sub-group is incompletely filled are paramagnetic. The magnetic moment in Bohr units is given by

$$\mu_B = g \sqrt{j(j+1)}$$

or $\mu_B = \sqrt{4s(s+1) + l(l+1)}$ which reduces to

$$\mu_B = \sqrt{4s(s+1)}$$

when the orbital moment is fully quenched. An examination of Table I will show that in the salts the experimental values of magnetic moment agree very closely with those calculated on the above formula for spin only.

TABLE I.
Magnetic moments of some metallic salts.

Salt	μ_B		No. of unpaired spins.	Salt.	μ_B		No of unpaired spins.
	Found	Calc.			Found.	Calc.	
CoBr_2	4.92	4.90	4	FeCl_2	5.79	5.92	5
MnCl_2	5.68	5.92	5	CrCl_2	4.90	4.90	4
MnBr_2	5.83	5.92	5	CrCl_3	4.05	3.87	3

The magnetic moment values for the oxides of the metals with completed inner shells are also in good agreement with theory, but with oxides of the transition metals, as will be seen from Table II, there is a wide divergence between the theoretical and the measured values. The divergence between the two values is so great that it makes the magnetic susceptibility method of determining valency a useless means.

TABLE II.

Magnetic moments of some metallic oxides.

Oxides.	μ_B		No. of unpaired spins.	Oxides.	μ_B		No. of unpaired spins.
	Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.	
MnO	2.78	3.87	3	Cr ₂ O ₃	2.12	3.87	3
MnO ₂	3.72	5.92	5	CrO ₂	0.344	0.00	0
Mn ₂ O ₃	3.53	4.90	4	CoO	2.91	4.9	4
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.96	5.92	5	CuO	0.90	1.73	1
				Cu ₂ O	0.447	0.00	0

It may also be that these divergencies between theory and practice are due to deviations from Curie's law, viz: $\chi_M = C_M / T$. In Curie's law no account is taken of the distortions produced by interatomic forces, and this factor is primarily responsible for the observed divergencies from theory. Weiss modified Curie's law to $\chi_M = C_M / (T - \theta)$, where θ takes cognizance of the molecular distortions. An attempt has been made in the present investigation to see whether the magnetic moments, calculated on the Weiss modification of the law, gives better concordance with theory. The observed values of μ_B have been utilised to discuss the molecular constitution of the cobalt oxides.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The reagents employed in the preparation of the oxides were of A. R. quality and the samples prepared were tested to be free from traces of ferromagnetic impurities. Because of the ease with which oxides adsorb gases, measures were taken to ensure that the samples obtained did not contain adsorbed gases. Before embarking on magnetic and chemical analysis, the samples were heated for prolonged intervals at 100° in *vacuo* and then allowed to cool in vacuum.

The methods of preparation and the results of analyses are as follows.

Methods of Preparation.

Cobaltous Oxide.—The specimens prepared by the following six methods have been studied.

(i) *Heating cobalt carbonate in vacuum* (Mobius Method, "Untersuchungen über Cobaltoxyde und deren Systeme mit Sauerstoff," Leipzig, 1929). Cobalt carbonate was heated under vacuum in a silica tube to about 900° in an electric furnace. The product obtained was allowed to cool in *vacuo*. The colour of the oxide was yellowish grey. Cobalt carbonate was obtained by the method of Mobius and others (Mobius *loc. cit.*, Bertrand, *Jahrb. Miner. Z.* ref. 161; H. de Sunarmont, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1851, 32, 153).

(ii) *Heating cobalt carbonate in carbon dioxide.* (Mobius, *loc. cit.*, Russel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1863, 16, 61; Winkelblech, *Annalen*, 1835, 113, 148, 253). Cobalt carbonate was electrically heated in an atmosphere of CO₂ to about 900° in a silica tube. The colour of the oxide was yellowish grey.

(iii) *Heating cobaltous hydroxide in CO₂.* (Blanc and Mobius, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, 142, 151; *Phys. Z.*, 1927, 32, 887, 288). Cobaltous hydroxide prepared according to the method of Huttig and Kassler (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 187, 16, 24) was heated electrically in a silica tube to 900° in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. The oxide obtained was yellowish grey in colour.

(iv) *Oxidising cobalt metal with nitric oxide* (Sabatier and Sanderens's method, *Compt. rend.*, 1892, 114, 1429). Cobalt metal obtained by the reduction of cobaltous oxide, Co₃O₄, by hydrogen at a temperature of 500° (Wohler and Balz, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1921, 27, 466) was heated at 150° in a stream of pure and dry nitric oxide gas. The oxide was greyish black in colour.

(v) *Reduction of cobaltic oxide in ammonia* (Vorster, "Ueber die Einwirkung des Ammoniaks auf die Oxyde des Nickel und Kobalt", Göttingen, 1861; Winkler, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1864, 91, 215). Cobaltic oxide obtained according to Winkelblech's method (*Annalen*, 1835, 13, 148, 253; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1935, 14, 6, 62) was heated at 350° in a current of dry ammonia. The colour of the oxide was brownish yellow.

(vi) *Reduction of cobaltous oxide with carbon.* (Kalmus's method, *Rep. Canadian Dept. Mines*, 1913, 259, 309; *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1914, 6, 115). Cobaltous oxide, prepared by electrically heating cobalt nitrate was heated with 2–3% of sugar charcoal at 900°. A greyish black product was obtained.

Cobaltous Oxide.—Cobaltous oxide was prepared by the following three methods :—

(i) *Heating cobalt nitrate* (Hempel, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1896, 11, 77; Remmler, *ibid.*, 1892, 2, 224). Cobaltous nitrate was first heated in an electric furnace at a low temperature and when the evolution of nitrogen peroxide gas ceased it was calcined at 800°—900°. The undecomposed nitrate was dissolved in water and the oxide dried.

(ii) *Calcining cobalt oxalate* (Rammelsberg's method, *Pogg. Ann.*, 1849, 78, 93). Cobalt oxalate was calcined at 900°.

(iii) *Heating a mixture of $\text{CoCl}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and NH_4Cl* . (Schwarzenberg, *Annalen*, 1825, 97, 212; Zimmermann, *ibid.*, 1886, 232, 335; Gorgen, *Compt. rend.*, 1855, 100, 175). A mixture of cobaltous chloride and ammonium chloride was heated to 500° in a silica tube. The product was digested with water to dissolve out the soluble salts and the oxide dried.

Cobaltic Oxide.—The following two methods were employed for the preparation of cobaltic oxide.

(i) *Calcination of cobalt nitrate at low temperatures*. (Proust and Winkelblech's method, *J. Phys.*, 1806, 63, 421). Cobaltous nitrate was calcined at 184° for a long time. The product was powdered and washed well with water, filtered and dried at a low temperature.

(ii) *Oxidising cobalt chloride with potassium chlorate*. (Thompson's method, *Chem. News*, 1863, 7, 184; *Z. anorg. Chem.* 1864, 3, 375; *Technologiste*, 1863, 24, 337). A concentrated aqueous solution of cobaltous chloride was mixed with one and a half parts of potassium chlorate and was slowly evaporated to dryness. The residue was heated at about 200° and the product so formed was extracted with water to remove soluble salts and finally dried at temperatures below 150°.

Analysis of the Oxides.

Cobalt in the various oxides was determined both by electrodeposition method and by cobalt sulphate method.

The amount of available oxygen in the oxides was determined by the iodine method. A known weight of the oxide was heated with an excess of hydrochloric acid. The chlorine evolved was absorbed in potassium iodide solution and the iodine thus liberated was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate solution.

The results of these analyses are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III.

Analysis of the oxides.

Oxide samples.		Cobalt		Available oxygen	
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Cobaltous oxide	I	78.589%	78.65%	—	0.000%
"	II	78.56	"	—	—
"	III	78.57	"	—	—
"	IV	79.02	"	—	—
"	V	78.14	"	0.085%	—
"	VI	78.264	"	0.099	—
Cobaltousic	I	73.33	73.43	6.639	6.642
"	II	73.38	"	6.638	"
"	III	73.32	"	6.640	"
Cobaltic	I	71.23	71.08	9.62	9.647
"	II	71.18	"	9.629	"

Magnetic Measurements.

The magnetic susceptibility values of the samples were determined on a modified form of Gouy's magnetic balance (Bhatnagar and Bal, *loc. cit.*, Gouy, *Compt. rend.*, 1889, 109, 935). The calculations of χ were made according to the equation,

$$\chi p_2 = \frac{I}{m p_1} \left\{ (\chi p_1 m p_1 - \chi_a m_a p_1) \frac{\omega p_2}{\omega p_1} + \chi_a m_a p_2 \right\}$$

where χp_1 and χp_2 are respectively the specific susceptibilities of the standard substance of the specimen and χ_a is the susceptibility of air, $m p_1$ and ωp_2 are the respective pulls, $m_a p_1$ and $m_a p_2$ are the masses of air displaced respectively by the standard substance and by the specimen.

The accuracy of the balance was tested by measuring the magnetic susceptibility of standard paramagnetics.

For measurements of magnetic susceptibility at higher temperatures an electrically heated silica tube furnace was used. The variations in temperature near the pole pieces on account of the furnace were found not to affect the field strength, because the pull per gram observed for a

standard diamagnetic, at various temperatures was found to be unaffected. In order to see whether the substance in the tube had actually attained the temperature recorded by the thermometer in the electric furnace, a magnetic examination of manganese pyrophosphate, prepared from analytically pure manganese sulphate, was undertaken. The calculation of temperature was made by the aid of the Curie-Weiss law,

$$\chi_M = \frac{C_M}{T - \theta}$$

the value of $\theta = 23^\circ$, being known for this compound.

The observed and the calculated temperatures are recorded below. The agreement is excellent.

TABLE IV.

Reading	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	
$\chi \times 10^6$	102.8	95.79	89.50	77.93	68.63	
Temp. {	Obs. ($^\circ\text{K}$)	300	324	348	404	461
	Calc. ($^\circ\text{K}$)	—	323	348	403.8	460.8

The magnetic susceptibilities of the cobaltous oxides are recorded in Table V and the variation of χ values with temperatures in Table VI, each value represents the mean of at least three independent observations. The Bohr magneton number μ_B is calculated from the formula $\mu_B = 2.839 \sqrt{\chi_M(T - \theta)}$ where χ_M corresponding to the observed χ is calculated for one metallic atom per molecule and θ , the Curie point is determined by plotting the $(1/\chi_M - T)$ graph and reading off θ as the intercept on the T -axis. In the case of cobaltous oxide the variation of $1/\chi_M$ with T is not linear below $80^\circ - 90^\circ$ and the value of θ was calculated from χ values at higher temperatures.

TABLE V.

Susceptibility of cobaltous oxide at 23° .

Method of preparation.	Colour.	χ .	Method of preparation.	Colour.	χ .
I	Yellowish grey	68.14×10^{-6}	IV	Greyish black	Ferro magnetic
II	„	68.14	V	Brownish black	57.49
III	„	68.45	VI	Greyish black	61.238

TABLE VI.

*Variation of Magnetic susceptibility with temperature.*1. *Cobaltous oxide.*(i) Sample prepared by heating cobalt carbonate in *vacuo*.

Temp.	χ .	χ_M .	θ from graph.	C_M calc.	C_M mean.	μ_B .
293°K	68.14×10^{-6}	5109.0×10^{-6}		3.199		
341	66.07	4953.0		3.339		
361	65.00	4873.0	-330°K	3.383	3.387	5.225
393	62.07	4654.0		3.379		
457	57.22	4289.0		3.388		
492	55.04	4127.0		3.397		

(ii) Sample prepared by heating cobalt carbonate in carbon dioxide.

296°K	68.74×10^{-6}	5153.0×10^{-6}		3.071		
324	68.21	5113.0		2.191		
348	66.89	5016.0		3.250		
355	66.13	4958.0		3.247		
			-300°K		3.243	5.113
375	64.28	4819.0		3.253		
398	62.12	4646.0		3.243		
465	56.28	4220.0		3.282		
495	54.28	4069.0		3.235		

(iii) Sample prepared by heating cobalt hydroxide in carbon dioxide.

296°K	68.45×10^{-6}	5133.0×10^{-6}		3.120		
325	66.02	5099.0		3.248		
348	66.03	4950.0		3.267		
355	65.33	4898.0		3.267		
			-312°K		3.207	5.131
375	63.22	4740.0		3.256		
398	61.35	4599.0		3.266		
465	55.97	4196.0		3.260		
495	54.26	4068.0		3.283		

TABLE VI (contd.).

2. Cobaltous oxide.

(i) Prepared by ignition of cobalt nitrate.

Temp.	χ .	χ_M .	θ from graph.	C_M calc.	C_M mean.	μ_M
293°K	30.73×10^{-8}	2468.0×10^{-8}		1.098		
314	29.47	2367.0		1.104		
340	27.81	2233.0		1.098		
			-152°K		1.101	2.979
395	25.03	2010.0		1.100		
154	22.58	1813.0		1.099		
105	20.82	1672.0		1.098		

(ii) Prepared by calcining cobalt oxalate.

293°K	30.63×10^{-8}	2460.0×10^{-8}		1.100		
301	30.00	2409.0		1.096		
313	29.39	2359.0		1.102		
			-154°K		1.102	2.981
338	27.93	2243.0		1.104		
393	25.42	2041.0		1.116		
457	22.51	1807.0		1.104		
503	20.63	1657.0		1.088		

(iii) Prepared by heating a mixture of cobalt and ammonium chlorides.

293°K	30.94×10^{-8}	2484.0×10^{-8}		1.108		
307	29.86	2397.0		1.104		
332	28.40	2280.0		1.106		
			-153°K		1.106	2.986
355	27.15	2180.0		1.108		
410	24.44	1963.0		1.104		
460	22.50	1807.0		1.108		
506	20.95	1683.0		1.109		

3. Cobaltic Oxide

(i) Sample prepared by heating cobalt nitrate at 184°.

293°K	28.63×10^{-8}	2375.0×10^{-8}		1.137		
319	27.01	2242.0		1.131		
341	26.05	2162.0		1.140		
			-186°K		1.136	3.026
393	23.66	1963.0		1.137		
457	21.27	1765.0		1.134		

(ii) Prepared by oxidising cobalt chloride with potassium chlorate.

296°K	28.08×10^{-8}	2405.0×10^{-8}		1.131		
323	27.46	2279.0		1.132		
			-174°K		1.132	3.021
349	25.93	2152.0		1.126		
397	23.95	1988.0		1.135		
461	21.51	1784.0		1.133		

DISCUSSION.

An examination of Tables V and VI shows that the samples of cobaltous oxide prepared by heating (i) cobalt carbonate in vacuum, (ii) cobalt carbonate in carbon dioxide, and (iii) cobaltous hydroxide in CO_2 , are all yellowish grey in colour and give a magnetic susceptibility value of $(68.45 \pm 0.30) \times 10^{-6}$ at 23° . It will be noticed that fairly constant values for χ are obtained in spite of the fact that the methods of preparation are different.

The cobaltous oxide, prepared by heating cobalt metal in a stream of nitric oxide at 150° (Table V, sample IV), is greyish black in colour and ferromagnetic; in oxide prepared by reduction of Co_3O_3 by NH_3 is brownish yellow, having a susceptibility value of 57.49×10^{-6} and the oxide (sample VI) prepared by the reduction of Co_3O_4 is greyish black and has a χ value of 61.238×10^{-6} .

The ferromagnetism of the oxide, prepared by heating cobalt metal in an atmosphere of NO , is attributable to the presence of some unreacted metal. This conclusion is supported by the analytical results shown in Table III which reveal the presence of free metal.

The low susceptibility value observed for cobaltous oxide, prepared by passing a current of ammonia over cobaltic oxide, may be due to (1) the presence of some higher oxide of cobalt or (2) more probably to a complex compound formed by the adsorption of ammonia on the oxide surface.

As regards the first possibility, the only higher oxide present, can be Co_3O_4 , since Co_2O_3 is not likely to exist at the temperature of the experiment. The calculated χ value of the sample on the assumption that it is a mixture of CoO and Co_3O_4 works out to 65.48×10^{-6} . The value actually obtained is 57.49×10^{-6} . It seems, therefore, that the low value of χ obtained for the product cannot be wholly accounted for by the formation of Co_3O_4 . The formation of some adsorption complex with ammonia is also suggested. Analytical results in fact did show the presence of ammonia in traces.

The sample VI (Table V) obtained by reduction of Co_3O_4 with carbon also gives a low χ value. Kalmuss (*loc. cit.*) has suggested that the oxide prepared in this manner is an allotropic modification of the ordinary cobaltous oxide but no evidence has been adduced to justify this assumption. The other possibility is that the difference in susceptibility may be due to the sample being a mixture or solid solution of different oxides; cobaltous and cobaltous oxides are known to exist in solid solution. The presence of Co_3O_4 will bring down the χ value of the oxide.

The calculated χ value for the sample on the assumption that it is a solid solution of the two oxides comes to be 65.36×10^{-6} . The observed χ is 61.26×10^{-6} and consequently magnetic evidence is against the mere formation of a simple solid solution of the two oxides. It is therefore suggested that this product is a complex of the type $\text{CoO} \cdot \text{NO}$ (*vide infra*).

The authors have studied the effect of temperature on the χ value of cobaltous oxide and the results are given in Table VI. The $(\chi/\chi_0, T)$ curves for the three samples of CoO show a discontinuity at $80^\circ\text{--}88^\circ$, indicating that a new phase makes its appearance at this temperature. The value of θ obtained by interpolation of the graphs from the susceptibility values beyond this temperature varied from 300° to 333° K.

The value of the Bohr magneton number, $\mu_B = 5.169 \pm 0.056$ is found to agree exceedingly well with the theoretical value for the cobaltous ion. The Co being in $4F\ 9/2$ state gives Bohr magneton number μ_B of 5.20 . If the orbital moment is fully quenched by a crystalline field, the spin moment alone is effective and the value of μ_B reduces to 3.87 . Since the experimental value is 5.169 ± 0.056 , it is clear that the cobalt ion in CoO is in the Co^{2+} state and the orbital moment is quite free to operate. Hence the molecular formula, CoO for cobaltous oxide, very well explains the known data about it. At temperatures below 80° , the value of μ_B moves in the direction of 'spin only'.

Squire (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, 7, 139) found that the paramagnetism of manganous oxide drops to nearly diamagnetism with decrease of temperature from 298° to 14°K and he expressed a similar view in explaining it.

Bhatnagar, King and collaborators (*loc. cit.*) observed a break in the χ - T curve for Cr_2O_3 at 65° and explained the anomaly in a similar manner.

Cobaltous and Cobaltic Oxides.

The cobaltous oxide shows a χ value of $(30.78 \pm 0.15) \times 10^{-6}$. The χ - T curve is smooth and the value of θ , obtained by interpolation, is -153 ± 1 . The Bohr magneton number μ_B is 2.982 ± 0.0035 . It is significant to note that in spite of the methods of preparation being different, the susceptibility value is constant for the compound.

The magnetic susceptibility of the two samples of Co_2O_3 has been determined. The values of χ for the two preparations of Co_2O_3 are 28.63×10^{-6} and 28.98×10^{-6} at 23° . The θ value found by interpolation on the χ - T curve was 186° and 174° and $\mu_B = 3.02$. Co is in $5D_4$ state. The theoretical value of the magnetic moment for trivalent cobalt ion lies between 4.9 and 5.48 . The experimental value, however, is much lower.

There is a great deal of uncertainty about the constitution of the oxide stated in literature to be Co_3O_3 . Mobius and Blanc (*loc.cit.*) doubt very much if cobaltic oxide can be produced by the dry methods. The alleged cobaltic oxide is considered to be a solid solution of oxygen in cobaltous oxide: cobaltous oxide adsorbs oxygen, forming the system $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4 \cdot m\text{O}_2$, and though the analysis makes it appear as Co_2O_3 , or even a higher oxide of cobalt, there is no change in the lattice structure of Co_3O_4 . Indeed Mobius has stated that all the methods described in literature for preparing cobaltic oxide really furnish solid solutions of the type $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4 \cdot m\text{O}_2$.

It seems that in cobaltous and cobaltic oxides the arrangement of the Co atom is just the same as that in CoO with the difference that in these oxides the orbital moments are fully quenched due to the combination of CoO molecules themselves. Now if that were the only change then the μ_s value would have been 3.87. The experimental value for Co_2O_3 is 3.02 and for Co_3O_4 2.98.

The adsorption of oxygen by CoO results in the lowering of the χ value (*vide infra*). It can therefore be inferred that the observed low value of μ_s for these oxides is due to the formation of complexes $3\text{CoO}\cdot\text{O}$ and $2\text{CoO}\cdot\text{O}$ respectively. The molecules of cobaltous and cobaltic oxides do not appear to exist as Co_3O_4 and Co_2O_3 .

The Effect of Oxygen Adsorption on CoO.

For the study of oxygen adsorption by cobaltous oxide the following procedure was adopted. Oxygen was passed over the oxide at different temperatures and the effect on χ value was determined. The exposed product was evacuated at (i) room temperature and (ii) the temperature at which adsorption was carried out and χ values again determined. The results are tabulated below (Table VII).

From Table VII it will be seen that originally the samples had no oxygen adsorbed on them since the χ value did not change on evacuation at 23° and at 100° . The susceptibility of the oxide uniformly decreases with the adsorption of oxygen and this effect becomes more marked at higher temperatures. Up to 80° the oxide regains more or less, its original value but when oxygen is passed at higher temperatures the value is not regained on evacuation.

The colour of the oxide also shows corresponding changes. Cobaltous oxide is yellowish grey but after oxygen adsorption it changes to brownish grey. Below 80° the oxide regains its original colour on evacuation, whereas the oxide treated at higher temperature undergoes a permanent change. Oxygen is adsorbed by CoO and a more or less loose adsorption complex

TABLE VII.

Treatment	Susceptibility values of cobaltous oxide samples ($\chi \times 10^6$).			Colour.
	I	II	III	
1. Evacuated at				
(i) 23°	68·14	65·73	68·44	Yellowish grey
(ii) 100°	68·14	68·744	68·445	„
2. Oxygen passed at				
23° for 1 hr.	68·03	68·60	68·160	„
Evacuated at 23°	68·12	68·71	68·41	„
3. (i) Oxygen passed at 80° for 1 hr.	67·28	67·39	67·33	Brownish tinge
(ii) Evacuated at				
(a) 23°	68·07	68·60	68·39	Yellowish grey
(b) 80°	68·08	68·71	68·401	„
4. (i) Oxygen passed at 120-30° for 1 hr.	65·42	65·80	65·47	Brownish yellowish grey
(ii) Evacuated at				
(a) 23°	66·01	66·31	66·12	A little less brownish tinge
(b) 120-30°	67·60	67·82	67·66	
5. (i) Oxygen passed at 200° for 2 hr.	46·64	46·89	46·245	Brownish grey
(ii) Evacuated at				
(a) 23°	48·00	48·14	48·16	„
(b) 200°	48·93	49·09	49·103	„

is formed which breaks up on evacuation but at higher temperatures there is a radical change. It seems therefore that below 80°, CoO adsorbs oxygen forming a loose adsorption complex or solid solution of the type $\text{CoO} \cdot n\text{O}_2$ which at higher temperatures passes into Co_3O_4 , this Co_3O_4 can further adsorb oxygen forming $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4 \cdot m\text{O}_2$. Now if the taking up of oxygen by CoO were purely a physical phenomenon then the susceptibility of the adsorption complex $\text{CoO} \cdot n\text{O}_2$ should increase because of the greater paramagnetism of oxygen ($107 \cdot 4 \times 10^{-6}$). The data given in Table VII, however, reveals that the susceptibility value of the complex has fallen. It appears therefore that the adsorption of oxygen by CoO is physicochemical in nature and the complex formed has low susceptibility value. The regaining of the original χ value after evacuation below 80° indicates that

the behaviour of $\text{CoO} \cdot n\text{O}_2$ complex is just like the palladium-hydrogen adsorption complex studied by Sveusson (*Ann. Physik*, 1933, 18, 299). At higher temperature the complex $\text{CoO} \cdot n\text{O}_2$ passes into relatively stable Co_3O_4 , this further adsorbs oxygen to form the complex $\text{Co}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot m\text{O}_2$ and finally cobaltic oxide. The changes that are involved on the adsorption of oxygen by CoO can be represented as follows.

Effect of Variation in Mode and Time of Heating on Cobaltous Oxide.

Cobaltous oxide was prepared by calcining cobaltous nitrate at about 800° - 900° in (i) electric furnace (*vide supra*) and (ii) blowpipe flame for different intervals of time. The samples of the oxide obtained were analysed for cobalt and the susceptibility values determined, the results obtained are given in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII.
Cobaltous oxide.

Mode of heating.	Time of heating.	Cobalt		Susceptibility values.
		Found.	Calc.	
Electric furnace	(a) 2 hrs.	73'34 %	73'43 %	$30'52 \times 10^{-8}$
	(b) 3 hrs.	73'333	"	30'58
	(c) 4 hrs. and upwards	73'364	"	30'554
Blowpipe	(a) 1 hr.	73'403	"	31'52
	(b) 2 hrs.	73'65	"	36'90
	(c) 3 hrs.	73'87	"	39'63
	(d) 4 hrs. and upwards	74'849	"	Ferromagnetic variety was obtained.

It will be seen from the results given in Table VIII that the samples prepared by heating cobalt nitrate in the electric furnace for different

intervals of time have the same χ values. The χ values for the second series of samples prepared in the blowpipe, however, shows a marked variation so much so that it was found possible to obtain finally a ferromagnetic variety. The change in the χ value in the latter case is due, no doubt to introduction of some soot particles from the blowpipe which reduced Co_3O_4 to CoO and finally to the metal itself. In order to test this view two sets of experiments were performed.

Some soot from the blowpipe was introduced into the electric furnace sample which was then heated for sometime in the electric furnace. This sample gave a χ value of 37.73×10^{-6} . On adding a further amount of soot and heating as before the χ -value obtained was 40.32×10^{-6} .

In another case cobalt nitrate was heated in a silica crucible with a lid, using a clear blow pipe flame for about 3 hours. Good care was taken that no soot particles had access to the oxide. The sample on analysis for cobalt gave 73.44% and showed a χ value of 31.46×10^{-6} . This value is higher than the values for pure Co_3O_4 (*vide supra*) so that the conclusion is irresistible that extreme care is necessary in order to avoid the formation of metal by reduction.

It is suggested that if due regard be paid to the purity of the oxides and if the distortions produced by interatomic forces are taken into consideration, magnetic measurements are capable of giving important evidence as to the structure of oxides, while even a slight impurity totally vitiates the conclusions.

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